

E-Banhatti Sombor Indices

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 03 December 2022	In this paper, we introduce the E-Banhatti Sombor index and the modified E-Banhatti Sombor index and their corresponding exponentials of a graph. Also we compute these newly defined E-Banhatti Sombor indices and their corresponding exponentials for wheel graphs, friendship graphs, tetrameric 1,3-adamantane and honeycomb networks. Furthermore, we establish some properties of the E-Banhatti Sombor index.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Let G be a simple, connected graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree $d_G(u)$ of a vertex u is the number of vertices adjacent to u . The edge e connecting the vertices u and v is denoted by uv . If $e=uv$ is an edge of G , then the vertex u and edge e are incident as are v and e . Let $d_G(e)$ denote the degree of an edge e in G , which is defined by $d_G(e) = d_G(u) + d_G(v) - 2$ with $e=uv$. We refer [1] for undefined term and notation.

A molecular graph is a simple graph, representing the carbon atom skeleton of an organic molecule of the hydrocarbon. Therefore the vertices of a molecular graph represent the carbon atoms and its edges the carbon-carbon bonds. Chemical Graph Theory is a branch of Mathematical Chemistry which has an important effect on the development of Chemical Sciences. Several graph indices [2] have found some applications in Chemistry, especially in QSPR/QSAR research [3, 4].

In [5], Kulli defined the Bhanhatti degree of a vertex u of a graph G as

$$B(u) = \frac{d_G(e)}{n - d_G(u)},$$

where n is the number of vertices of G and the vertex u and edge e are incident in G .

The first and second E-Banhatti indices were introduced by Kulli in [5] and they are defined as

$$EB_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [B(u) + B(v)],$$

$$EB_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} B(u)B(v).$$

In [6], the FE-Banhatti index of a graph G is defined as

$$FEB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [B(u)^2 + B(v)^2].$$

Recently, some E-Banhatti indices were studied, for example, in [7, 8].

We propose the E-Banhatti Sombor index of a graph G and defined it as

$$EBS(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}.$$

Considering the E-Banhatti Sombor index, we define the E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of a graph G as

$$EBS(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}}.$$

We propose the modified E-Banhatti Sombor index of a graph G and defined it as

$${}^m EBS(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}}.$$

Considering the modified E-Banhatti Sombor index, we define the modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of a graph G as

$${}^m EBS(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}}}.$$

Several types of topological or graph indices such as distance based, degree based indices have been introduced and studied in Chemical Graph Theory. Among graph indices Wiener, Zagreb, Gourava, Revan, Reverse, Banhatti indices are studied well. In [5], Kulli defined Banhatti degree of a vertex in a graph and introduced the first and second E-Banhatti indices of a graph. A study of E-Banhatti indices in Chemical Graph Theory is a new direction in Graph Index Theory.

In Chemical Graph Theory, several graph indices were introduced and studied such as the Wiener index [9, 10, 11, 12, 13], the Zagreb indices [14, 15, 16, 17, 18], the Revan indices [19, 20, 21, 22], the reverse indices [23, 24, 25], the Gourava indices [26, 27, 28, 29] and the Banhatti indices [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35].

In this paper, we compute the E-Banhatti Sombor and modified E-Banhatti Sombor indices for some standard graphs, wheel graphs, friendship graphs, tetrameric 1,3-adamantane and honeycomb networka.

II. RESULTS FOR SOME STANDARD GRAPHS

Proposition 1. If G is an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$, then

$$EBS(G) = \frac{\sqrt{2nr(r-1)}}{(n-r)}$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$.

Then G has $\frac{nr}{2}$ edges. For any edge $uv=e$ in G , $d_G(e) = d_G(u) + d_G(v) - 2 = 2r - 2$.

From definition we have

$$\begin{aligned} EBS(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2} \\ &= \frac{nr}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{2r-2}{n-r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2r-2}{n-r}\right)^2} = \frac{\sqrt{2nr(r-1)}}{(n-r)}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$EBS(C_n) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}n}{(n-2)}$$

Corollary 1.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$EBS(K_n) = \sqrt{2}n(n-1)(n-2)$$

Proposition 2. Let P_n be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$\begin{aligned} EBS(P_n) &= 2\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n-1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2}{n-2}\right)^2} \\ &\quad + (n-3)\sqrt{\left(\frac{2}{n-2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2}{n-2}\right)^2} \\ &= \frac{2\sqrt{5n^2 - 12n + 8}}{(n-1)(n-2)} + \frac{2\sqrt{2}(n-3)}{(n-2)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3. Let $K_{m,n}$ be a complete bipartite graph with $1 \leq m \leq n$ and $n \geq 2$. Then

$$EBS(K_{m,n}) = \sqrt{(m^2 + n^2)(m + n - 2)^2}$$

Proof: Let $K_{m,n}$ be a complete bipartite $m \ n$ graph with $m + n$ vertices and mn edges such that $|V_1| = m, |V_2| = n, V(K_{r,s}) = V_1 \square V_2$ for $1 \leq m \leq n$, and $n \geq 2$. Every vertex of V_1 is incident with n edges and every vertex of V_2 is incident with m edges. Then $d_G(e) = d_G(u) + d_G(v) - 2 = m + n - 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} EBS(K_{m,n}) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2} \\ &= mn \sqrt{\left(\frac{m+n-2}{m+n-n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{m+n-2}{m+n-m}\right)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{(m^2 + n^2)(m + n - 2)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.1. Let $K_{n,n}$ be a complete bipartite graph with $n \geq 2$. Then

$$EBS(K_{n,n}) = 2\sqrt{2}n(n-1)$$

Corollary 3.2. Let $K_{1,n}$ be a star with $n \geq 2$. Then

$$EBS(K_{1,n}) = (n-1)\sqrt{1+n^2}$$

Proposition 4. If G is an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$, then

$${}^m EBS(G) = \frac{nr(n-r)}{4\sqrt{2}(r-1)}$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$.

Then G has $\frac{nr}{2}$ edges. For any edge $uv=e$ in G , $d_G(e) = d_G(u) + d_G(v) - 2 = 2r - 2$.

From definition we have

$${}^m EBS(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [B(u)^2 + B(v)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$= \frac{nr}{2} \left[\left(\frac{2r-2}{n-r} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{2r-2}{n-r} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{nr(n-r)}{4\sqrt{2}(r-1)}.$$

Corollary 4.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$${}^m EBS(C_n) = \frac{n(n-2)}{2\sqrt{2}}.$$

Corollary 4.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$${}^m EBS(K_n) = \frac{n(n-1)}{4\sqrt{2}(n-2)}.$$

Proposition 5. Let P_n be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m EBS(P_n) &= 2 \left[\left(\frac{1}{n-1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{2}{n-2} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad + (n-3) \left[\left(\frac{2}{n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{2}{n-2} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \frac{2(n-1)(n-2)}{\sqrt{5n^2 - 12n + 8}} + \frac{(n-3)(n-2)}{2\sqrt{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 6. Let $K_{m,n}$ be a complete bipartite graph with $1 \leq m \leq n$ and $n \geq 2$. Then

$${}^m EBS(K_{m,n}) = \frac{m^2 n^2}{\sqrt{(m^2 + n^2)(m+n-2)^2}}.$$

Proof: Let $K_{m,n}$ be a complete bipartite $m \times n$ graph with $m+n$ vertices and mn edges such that $|V_1|=m, |V_2|=n, V(K_{r,s}) = V_1 \square V_2$ for $1 \leq m \leq n$, and $n \geq 2$. Every vertex of V_1 is incident with n edges and every vertex of V_2 is incident with m edges. Then $d_G(e) = d_G(u) + d_G(v) - 2 = m + n - 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m EBS(K_{m,n}) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left[B(u)^2 + B(v)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= mn \left[\left(\frac{m+n-2}{m+n-n} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{m+n-2}{m+n-m} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \frac{m^2 n^2}{\sqrt{(m^2 + n^2)(m+n-2)^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 6.1. Let $K_{n,n}$ be a complete bipartite graph with $n \geq 2$. Then

$${}^m EBS(K_{n,n}) = \frac{n^3}{2\sqrt{2}(n-1)}.$$

Corollary 6.2. Let $K_{1,n}$ be a star with $n \geq 2$. Then

$${}^m EBS(K_{1,n}) = \frac{n^2}{(n-1)\sqrt{1+n^2}}.$$

III. RESULTS FOR WHEEL GRAPHS

A wheel graph W_n is the join of C_n and K_1 . Then W_n has $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. A graph W_n is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Wheel graph W_n

In W_n , there are two types of edges as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d(u) = d(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d(u) = 3, d(v) = n\}, \quad |E_2| = n.$$

Therefore, in W_n , there are two types of Bhanhatti edges based on Bhanhatti degrees of end vertices of each edge follow:

$$BE_1 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{4}{(n-2)}\}, \quad |BE_1| = n.$$

$$BE_2 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid B(u) = \frac{n+1}{n-2}, B(v) = n+1\}, \quad |BE_2| = n.$$

We compute the E-Banhatti Sombor index of the wheel graph W_n .

Theorem 1. Let W_n be a wheel graph with $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. Then

$$EBS(W_n) = \frac{n}{n-2} \left(4\sqrt{2} + (n+1)\sqrt{n^2 - 4n + 5} \right).$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Bhanhatti edge partition of W_n , we obtain

$$EBS(W_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}$$

$$= n \sqrt{\left(\frac{4}{n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{n-2} \right)^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+n\sqrt{\left(\frac{n+1}{n-2}\right)^2 + (n+1)^2} \\
 &= \frac{n}{n-2} \left(4\sqrt{2} + (n+1)\sqrt{(n^2 - 4n + 5)} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

We compute the modified E-Banhatti Sombor index of the wheel graph W_n .

Theorem 2. Let W_n be a wheel graph with $n + 1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. Then

$${}^m EBS(W_n) = n(n-2) \left[\frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2 - 4n + 5}} \right].$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of W_n , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m EBS(W_n) &= \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}} \\
 &= n \left[\left(\frac{4}{n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{n-2} \right)^2 \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &+ n \left[\left(\frac{n+1}{n-2} \right)^2 + (n+1)^2 \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\
 &= n(n-2) \left[\frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2 - 4n + 5}} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of a wheel graph W_n , we obtain the E-Banhattil Sombor and modified SE-Banhatti Sombor exponentials of W_n .

Theorem 3. The E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of W_n is given by

$$EBS(W_n, x) = nx^{n-2} + nx^{\frac{4\sqrt{2}}{n-2} + \frac{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2-4n+5}}{n-2}}.$$

Theorem 4. The modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of W_n is given by

$${}^m EBS(W_n, x) = nx^{\frac{n-2}{4\sqrt{2}}} + nx^{\frac{n-2}{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2-4n+5}}}.$$

IV. RESULTS FOR FRIENDSHIP GRAPHS

A friendship graph F_n , $n \geq 2$, is a graph that can be constructed by joining n copies of C_3 with a common vertex. A graph F_4 is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Friendship graph F_4

Let F_n be a friendship graph with $2n+1$ vertices and $3n$ edges. By calculation, we obtain that there are two types of edges as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid d_{F_n}(u) = d_{F_n}(v) = 2\}, \quad |E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid d_{F_n}(u) = 2, d_{F_n}(v) = 2n\}, \quad |E_2| = 2n.$$

Therefore, in F_n , there are two types of Banhatti edges based on Banhatti degrees of end vertices of each edge follow:

$$BE_1 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{2}{2n-1}\}, \quad |BE_1| = n.$$

$$BE_2 = \{uv \in E(F_n) \mid B(u) = \frac{2n}{2n-1}, B(v) = 2n\}, \quad |BE_2| = n.$$

We compute the E-Banhatti Sombor index of the friendship graph F_n .

Theorem 5. Let F_n be a friendship graph with $n + 1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. Then

$$EBS(F_n) = \frac{n}{n-2} \left(4\sqrt{2} + (n+1)\sqrt{n^2 - 4n + 5} \right).$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of F_n , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 EBS(F_n) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2} \\
 &= n\sqrt{\left(\frac{4}{n-2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{n-2}\right)^2} \\
 &+ n\sqrt{\left(\frac{n+1}{n-2}\right)^2 + (n+1)^2} \\
 &= \frac{n}{n-2} \left(4\sqrt{2} + (n+1)\sqrt{(n^2 - 4n + 5)} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

We compute the modified E-Banhatti Sombor index of the friendship graph F_n .

Theorem 6. Let F_n be a friendship graph with $n + 1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. Then

$${}^m EBS(F_n) = n(n-2) \left[\frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2-4n+5}} \right].$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of F_n , we have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m EBS(F_n) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_n)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}} \\ &= n \left[\left(\frac{4}{n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{n-2} \right)^2 \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad + n \left[\left(\frac{n+1}{n-2} \right)^2 + (n+1)^2 \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= n(n-2) \left[\frac{1}{4\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2-4n+5}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of a friendship graph F_n , we obtain the E- Banhatti Sombor and modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponentials of F_n .

Theorem 7. The E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of F_n is given by

$$EBS(F_n, x) = nx^{n-2} + nx^{\frac{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2-4n+5}}{n-2}}.$$

Theorem 8. The modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of F_n is given by

$${}^m EBS(F_n, x) = nx^{\frac{n-2}{4\sqrt{2}}} + nx^{\frac{n-2}{(n+1)\sqrt{n^2-4n+5}}}.$$

V.RESULTS FOR TETRAMERIC 1,3-ADAMANTANE

In Chemistry, diamondoids are variants of the carbon cage known as adamantane (C₁₀, H₁₆), the smallest unit cage structure of the diamond crystal lattice. We focus on the molecular graph structure of the family of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane, denoted by $TA[n]$. Let G be the graph of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[n]$. The graph of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[4]$ is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

By calculation, G has $10n$ vertices and $13n - 1$ edges. Also by calculation, we obtain three edge partitions of G based on the degrees of the end vertices of each edge as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u)=2, d_G(v)=3\}, |E_1| = 6n + 6. \\ E_2 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u)=2, d_G(v)=4\}, |E_2| = 6n - 6. \\ E_3 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u)=d_G(v) = 4\}, |E_3| = n - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, in $TA[n]$, there are three types of edges based on the temperature of end vertices of each edge as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} BE_1 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid B(u) = \frac{3}{10n-2}, B(v) = \frac{3}{10n-3}\}, \\ |BE_1| &= 6n+6. \\ BE_2 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid B(u) = \frac{4}{10n-2}, B(v) = \frac{4}{10n-4}\}, \\ |BE_2| &= 6n-6. \\ BE_3 &= \{uv \in E(G) \mid B(u) = \frac{6}{10n-4}, B(v) = \frac{6}{10n-4}\}, \\ |BE_3| &= n-1. \end{aligned}$$

We compute the E-Banhatti Sombor index of $TA[n]$.

Theorem 9. Let G be the graph of a tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[n]$ with $10n$ vertices and $13n-1$ edges. Then

$$\begin{aligned} EBS(TA[n]) &= \frac{3(6n+6)\sqrt{(10n-2)^2 + (10n-3)^2}}{(10n-2)(10n-3)} \\ &\quad + \frac{2(6n-6)\sqrt{(5n-1)^2 + (5n-2)^2}}{(5n-1)(5n-2)} \\ &\quad + \frac{3\sqrt{2}(n-1)}{(5n-2)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of $TA[n]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} EBS(TA[n]) &= \sum_{uv \in E(TA[n])} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2} \\ &= (6n+6) \sqrt{\left(\frac{3}{10n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{3}{10n-3} \right)^2} \\ &\quad + (6n-6) \sqrt{\left(\frac{4}{10n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2} \\ &\quad + (n-1) \sqrt{\left(\frac{6}{10n-4} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{6}{10n-4} \right)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

After simplification, we get the desired result.

We compute the modified E-Banhatti Sombor index of $TA[n]$.

Theorem 10. Let G be the graph of a tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[n]$ with $10n$ vertices and $13n-1$ edges. Then

$${}^m EBS(TA[n]) = \frac{(6n+6)(10n-2)(10n-3)}{3\sqrt{(10n-2)^2+(10n-3)^2}} + \frac{(6n-6)(5n-1)(5n-2)}{2\sqrt{(5n-1)^2+(5n-2)^2}} + \frac{(n-1)(5n-2)}{3\sqrt{2}}.$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of $TA[n]$, we have

$${}^m EBS(TA[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(TA[n])} \frac{1}{\sqrt{B(u)^2+B(v)^2}} = (6n+6) \left[\left(\frac{3}{10n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{3}{10n-3} \right)^2 \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} + (6n-6) \left[\left(\frac{4}{10n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} + (n-1) \left[\left(\frac{4}{10n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

gives the desired result after simplification.

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of a friendship graph $TA[n]$, we obtain the E-Banhatti Sombor and modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponentials of $TA[n]$.

Theorem 11. The E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of $TA[n]$ is given by

$$EBS(TA[n], x) = (6n+6)x^{\frac{3\sqrt{(10n-2)^2+(10n-3)^2}}{(10n-2)(10n-3)}} + (6n-6)x^{\frac{2\sqrt{(5n-1)^2+(5n-2)^2}}{(5n-1)(5n-2)}} + (n-1)x^{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{(5n-2)}}.$$

Theorem 12. The modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of $TA[n]$ is given by

$${}^m EBS(TA[n], x) = (6n+6)x^{\frac{(10n-2)(10n-3)}{3\sqrt{(10n-2)^2+(10n-3)^2}}}$$

$$+ (6n-6)x^{\frac{(5n-1)(5n-2)}{2\sqrt{(5n-1)^2+(5n-2)^2}}} + (n-1)x^{\frac{5n-2}{3\sqrt{2}}}.$$

VI. RESULTS FOR HONEYCOMB NETWORKS

Honeycomb networks are useful in Computer Graphics and Chemistry. A honeycomb network of dimension n is denoted by HC_n , where n is the number of hexagons between central and boundary hexagon. A 4-dimensional honeycomb network is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. A 4-dimensional honeycomb network

Let G be the graph of a honeycomb network HC_n . By calculation, we obtain that G has $6n^2$ vertices and $9n^2-3n$ edges. In G , by algebraic method, there are three types of edges based on the degree of end vertices of each edge as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(HC_n) \mid d_G(u) = d_G(v) = 2\}, \quad |E_1| = 6, \\ E_2 = \{uv \in E(HC_n) \mid d_G(u) = 2, d_G(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_2| = 12n - 12, \\ E_3 = \{uv \in E(HC_n) \mid d_G(u) = d_G(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_3| = 9n^2 - 15n + 6.$$

Therefore, in HC_n , there are three types of Banhatti edges based on Banhatti degrees of end vertices of each edge as follow:

$$BE_1 = \{uv \in E(HC_n) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{2}{6n^2-2}\}, \quad |BE_1| = 6, \\ BE_2 = \{uv \in E(HC_n) \mid B(u) = \frac{2}{6n^2-2}, B(v) = \frac{3}{6n^2-3}\}, \quad |BE_2| = 12n - 12, \\ BE_3 = \{uv \in E(HC_n) \mid B(u) = B(v) = \frac{4}{6n^2-3}\}, \quad |BE_3| = 9n^2 - 15n + 6.$$

We now compute the E-Banhatti Sombor index of a honeycomb network HC_n .

Theorem 13. Let G be the graph of a honeycomb network HC_n with $6n^2$ vertices and $9n^2 - 15n + 6$ edges. Then

$$EBS(HC_n) = \frac{12\sqrt{2}}{6n^2 - 2} + \frac{3(12n - 12)\sqrt{(6n^2 - 2)^2 + (6n^2 - 3)^2}}{(6n^2 - 2)(6n^2 - 3)} + \frac{4\sqrt{2}(9n^2 - 15n + 6)}{6n^2 - 3}.$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of HC_n , we obtain

$$EBS(HC_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(HC_n)} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2} = 6\sqrt{\left(\frac{2}{6n^2 - 2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2}{6n^2 - 2}\right)^2} + (12n - 12)\sqrt{\left(\frac{3}{6n^2 - 2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{3}{6n^2 - 3}\right)^2} + (9n^2 - 15n + 6)\sqrt{\left(\frac{4}{6n^2 - 3}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{6n^2 - 3}\right)^2}.$$

After simplification, we get the desired result.

We now compute the modified E-Banhatti Sombor index of a honeycomb network HC_n .

Theorem 14. Let G be the graph of a honeycomb network HC_n with $6n^2$ vertices and $9n^2 - 15n + 6$ edges. Then

$${}^m EBS(HC_n) = \frac{3(6n^2 - 2)}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{(4n - 4)(6n^2 - 2)(6n^2 - 3)}{\sqrt{(6n^2 - 2)^2 + (6n^2 - 3)^2}} + \frac{(9n^2 - 15n + 6)(6n^2 - 3)}{4\sqrt{2}}.$$

Proof: From definition and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of HC_n , we have

$${}^m EBS(HC_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(HC_n)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2}} = 6\left[\left(\frac{2}{6n^2 - 2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2}{6n^2 - 2}\right)^2\right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} + (12n - 12)\left[\left(\frac{3}{6n^2 - 2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{3}{6n^2 - 3}\right)^2\right]^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$+ (9n^2 - 15n + 6)\left[\left(\frac{4}{6n^2 - 3}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{6n^2 - 3}\right)^2\right]^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

gives the desired result after simplification.

By using definitions and by cardinalities of the Banhatti edge partition of a friendship graph HC_n , we obtain the E-Banhatti Sombor and modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponentials of HC_n .

Theorem 15. The E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of HC_n is given by

$$EBS(HC_n, x) = 6x^{\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{6n^2 - 2}} + (12n - 12)x^{\frac{3\sqrt{(6n^2 - 2)^2 + (6n^2 - 3)^2}}{(6n^2 - 2)(6n^2 - 3)}} + (9n^2 - 15n + 6)x^{\frac{4\sqrt{2}}{6n^2 - 3}}.$$

Theorem 16. The modified E-Banhatti Sombor exponential of HC_n is given by

$${}^m EBS(HC_n, x) = 6x^{\frac{6n^2 - 2}{2\sqrt{2}}} + (12n - 12)x^{\frac{(6n^2 - 2)(6n^2 - 3)}{3\sqrt{(6n^2 - 2)^2 + (6n^2 - 3)^2}}} + (9n^2 - 15n + 6)x^{\frac{6n^2 - 3}{4\sqrt{2}}}.$$

VII. PROPERTIES OF E-BANHATTI SOMBOR INDEX

Theorem 17. Let G be a connected graph with m edges. Then

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} EB_1(G) \leq EBS(G) \leq EB_1(G).$$

Proof: For any two positive numbers a and b ,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(a + b) \leq \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \leq a + b.$$

For $a=B(u)$ and $b=B(v)$, the above inequalities transform into

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(B(u) + B(v)) \leq \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2} \leq B(u) + B(v)$$

Now, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (B(u)+B(v)) &\leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{(B(u))^2+B(v)^2} \\ &\leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (B(u)+B(v)) \end{aligned}$$

with the help of definitions, we arrive the desired result.

Theorem 18. Let G be a connected graph with m edges. Then

$$EBS(G) \leq \sqrt{mFEB(G)}.$$

Proof: Using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{B(u)^2 + B(v)^2} \right)^2 &\leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} 1 \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (B(u)^2 + (v)^2). \\ &= mFEB(G). \end{aligned}$$

Thus
$$EBS(G) \leq \sqrt{mFEB(G)}.$$

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced the E-Banhatti Sombor index, modified E-Banhatti Sombor index and their corresponding exponentials of a graph. We have computed these newly defined indices and exponentials for some standard graphs, wheel graphs, friendship graphs and certain nanostructures. This study is a new direction in Graph Indices.

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V. Results for H-Naphtalenic Nanotubes

In this section we consider a family of H -Naphtalenic nanotubes. This nanotube is a trivalent decoration having a sequence of $C_6, C_6, C_4, C_6, C_6, C_4, \dots$ in the first row and a sequence of $C_6, C_8, C_6, C_8, \dots$ in other row. This nanotube is denoted by $NHPX[m, n]$, where m is the number of pair of hexagons in first row and n is the number of alternative hexagons in a column as shown in Figure 4.

$6n + 6$

$6n - 6$

$n - 1$
